

FROM SCREEN TO SHELVES: MILLENNIALS' PATRONAGE DECISION TOWARDS SKINCARE PRODUCTS IN CARMONA, CAVITE

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From Screen to Shelves: Millennials' Patronage Decision Towards Skincare Products in Carmona, Cavite

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Abstract

This study was conducted with an aim to determine the most used Korean skincare product brand of millennials; the influence level of product placement in Korean drama in terms of prominence, modality and celebrity endorsement; the influence level of word-of-mouth promotion in terms of traditional and electronic word of mouth; and their level of patronage decision. Likewise, the relationship between the said variables were also assessed. The study utilized quota, purposive, and snowball sampling techniques in gathering information through a modified research questionnaire from the 210 participants. Frequency count and percentage, weighted mean and standard deviation, and Chi-square test were used to interpret and analyze data. Findings revealed that the most used Korean skincare product brand of the participants is Innisfree. In addition, prominence and celebrity endorsement were found to be highly influential in Korean drama's product placement. While both the traditional and electronic word-of-mouth were found to be highly influential. Moreover, millennials have a very high level of patronage decision towards skincare products. Furthermore, the results also revealed that product placement in Korean drama have a significant relationship to the patronage decision of the participants the same with the word-of-mouth promotion in terms of traditional and electronic word of mouth which were also found be significantly related to the patronage decision. This clearly implicates that participants' patronage decision were extremely affected and influenced by the promotional activities particularly product placement in Korean drama and word of mouth promotion towards Korean skincare products.

Keywords: *product placement, word-of-mouth, korean drama, korean skin care products*

Introduction

Nowadays, most of the Filipinos are familiar with Hallyu wave – a term known as Korean wave, which refers to the rising popularity of Korean culture across the world. As mentioned by Parc and Moon (2013), Korean dramas are one of the factors that help Korean culture gains it momentum. Likewise, based on Korean Foundation, the said dramas are very popular to the country making the Philippines as the country which has the highest number of Hallyu fans among 113 countries. Furthermore, during the pandemic where everyone is prohibited to go outside, many Filipinos tend to entertain themselves by watching Korean dramas. According to Adel (2020), there is huge increase on streaming of the said dramas after the implementation of quarantine in the Philippines.

Korean drama is known in using a modern strategy of promotion which is called product placement. The scenes involve product promotions that blended well to the storyline of the drama which makes the viewers to be consciously aware of the product. Placing of product into shows is an innovative way to affect purchases of consumers as it was subtly introduced (Bhasin, 2021). Likewise, Korean dramas have a huge influence to Filipinos in terms of food, fashion, cosmetics, skin cares, music, and entertainment industries, as well as to people's views and preferences. These shows also influence the Filipinos in terms of beauty industry as Koreans present in the scenes have glass skin which attracted them as a viewer.

Korean beauty is a term known for skincare products and beauty regimen. Korean skincare products contain natural ingredients found on plants and even in animals suitable for any skin types which can be used on a long term basis to see effects. That is, it cannot be denied that the increase of the demand of Korean beauty products was due to the placement of the product in Korean dramas. Correspondingly, the demand for Korean beauty products of the Filipinos is increasing which makes the imports of South Korean beauty products to grow by 26.58 million US dollars in the year 2017 (Janio Content Team, 2019). This also made the survey conducted by Rakuten Insight to have a stronger result as it reveals that majority of the Filipinos use Korean skincare products as of the year 2019 (Sanchez, 2019).

Aside from product placement in Korean dramas, word of mouth promotion is a free marketing strategy triggered by customer experiences that shape their attitudes to manifest intentions and behaviors of re- patronization and recommendation (Hayes, 2021). This strategy has two types: the traditional and the electronic word of mouth. Moreover, majority of the Filipinos purchase Korean skincare products due to the influence of positive recommendations coming from their family and friends (Sanchez, 2019). In the digital age, word of mouth is indeed a great marketing strategy for Korean products. Consumers became more interested in Korean beauty products because they used the internet like official websites, dramas on YouTube and reviews from many people to gather information about it (Moslehpour, 2017).

In keeping with the study of Bradtke (2019), it was revealed that the heavy buyers of these skincare products are millennials. In an article published by Gandia (2017) and as stated by Ingels (2020), the immense success of Korean wave made the audiences to be immersed on other K-branded products such as K-food and K- beauty. The said viewers pertain to millennials who are also the main

consumers of Korean drama. In addition, the age bracket for this generation is between 23 to 38 years old as mentioned by Dimmock (2019) in Pew Research Center.

Due to the growing popularity of Korean wave in the country which is evident on the data mentioned above in terms of the population of millennial as Korean drama fans and as consumers of Korean skincare products, the researchers intend to conduct this study. The present study will determine the influence of product placement in Korean drama and word of mouth promotion on patronage decision of millennials towards Korean skincare products in Carmona, Cavite. This study might be beneficial to Korean, local companies, and marketers in order for them to identify which among the factors of product placement in Korean drama and word of mouth promotion have a significant influence on patronage decision.

Research Questions

The purpose of this study was to determine if product placement in Korean drama and word of mouth promotion influences the patronage decision of millennials towards Korean skincare products in Carmona, Cavite. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the most used Korean skincare product brand of millennials in Carmona, Cavite:
 - 1.1. Laneige;
 - 1.2. Innisfree;
 - 1.3. Mediheal;
 - 1.4. Manyo Factory;
 - 1.5. CNP Laboratory;
 - 1.6. Klavvu; and
 - 1.7. Colorgram?
2. What is the level of influence of product placement in Korean drama on millennials in Carmona, Cavite towards Korean skincare products in terms of:
 - 2.1. prominence;
 - 2.2. modality; and
 - 2.3. celebrity endorsement?
3. What is the level of influence of word-of-mouth promotion of Korean skincare products on millennials in Carmona, Cavite in terms of:
 - 3.1. traditional word of mouth; and
 - 3.2. electronic word of mouth?
4. What is the level of patronage decision of millennials in Carmona, Cavite towards Korean skincare products?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the level of influence of product placement in Korean drama and the level of patronage decision of millennials in Carmona, Cavite towards Korean skincare products in terms of:
 - 5.1. prominence and patronage decision;
 - 5.2. modality and patronage decision; and
 - 5.3. celebrity endorsement and patronage decision?
6. Is there a significant relationship between the level of influence of word-of-mouth promotion and the level of patronage decision of millennials in Carmona, Cavite towards Korean skincare products in terms of:
 - 6.1. traditional word of mouth and patronage decision; and
 - 6.2. electronic word of mouth and patronage decision?

Literature Review

Korean Skincare Products

Given that Korean dramas appear in the Philippine entertainment industry, most Filipinos imitate the Korean culture. Millennials tend to mimic the fashion sense of Korean celebrities and even the skincare products that every actor and actress used in the dramas. According to Ridder (2020), skincare products are one of the main product categories and the most demanded product of cosmetic market having a 39 percent share in the market. It is indeed the most profitable category as its market value grows to 20.1 billion dollars as of the year 2019. In addition, cosmetics are products that are not only makeup related but for enhancing and taking good care of the face and body as well. These products may include moisturizers and cleansers. Also, Rancho (2020) mentioned that Dr. Margarita Lolis, Dr. Debra Jaliman, and Dr. Brandith Irwin, dermatologists, cited that Korean skincare products that are tested and considered the most commonly used skincare products include cleanser, moisturizer, toner, serum, face mask, eye cream, sunscreen, and etc.

Patronage Decision

Patronage decision refers to the behavior of the consumers to purchase again the Korean skincare products they have used or bought through online or physical store. Through Korean dramas, it influences the patronage decision of millennials towards Korean skincare. According to Biagtan (2020), many Filipino women aim to have a lighter skin as they imitate Korean beauty trends and purchase

Korean skincare products that are exposed in Korean dramas. Herman et al. (2016) said that the popularity of Korean dramas has increased recognition and gained interest of the public towards Korean skincare products. Korean dramas create an impact on the view of millennials and they began to consume products and follow beauty routines of Korean celebrities (Biagtan, 2020). Consumers also seek information from friends or searching on the internet about the skincare product before purchasing it.

Relationship of Product Placement and Patronage Decision

Utomo and Suprajitno (2020) defined product placement as a type of sponsor paid blended promotion in films, shows, television programs, radio, and even in theater performances wherein placement of a product, brand, or situation creates a certain behavior. In the study of Kumar (2017), audiences preferred the placement of the product if it is well integrated to the storyline or when their desired celebrities use it naturally in the scene. They were positively influenced when they hardly notice the product placement or while watching the said promotion, it does not cause any distractions. As a result, most of the people purchase the product when they see it as product placement, but not all of them.

Bhasin (2021) argued the same that product placement enables the product to be visibly shown more to the audience. Marketers innovated the way of placing the products into subtler way as the frequent exposure of products becomes a distraction minimizer for the audiences.

Prominence. Bhasin (2021) characterized prominence as a level of placed product's ability to catch the attention of the viewers. This can be divided into two types: low (subtle) and high (prominent) prominence. According to Hansson and Mattsson (2017), subtle placement refers to the type of product placement. The placed products are well integrated to the plot or the placement is well blended to the storyline.

Modality. Utomo and Suprajitno (2020) stated that the usage of audio-visual modality conveys the hidden message of the company to deliver product placement in Korean drama. In Korean dramas like *Goblin*, it is an innovative way that effectively influences the viewers which further leads them to buy the product.

Celebrity endorsement. Product placements that are displayed in movies as well as on television shows grab the attention of the viewers and help in creating acceptance for the brand. It eventually leads to brand recall among the consumers while they are shopping and on deciding what to purchase. Also, they find out about the other factors that are connected and contribute to product placement which include celebrity endorsements, references, and emotions (Kumar, 2017).

Relationship of Traditional Word-of-Mouth Promotion and Patronage Decision

Corresponding to Huete (2017), traditional word-of-mouth provides a personal and real-time based exchange which leads to a more credible exchange. In addition, it stated that word-of-mouth is typically considered face-to-face spoken communication, although telephone conversations, text messages sent via SMS, and web dialogue, such as online profile pages, blog posts, instant messages, and e-mails are also included in the purview of word-of-mouth communication.

In the research of Rosario (2020), the interest in Korean movies and music increases the word-of-mouth communication about Korean wave, and by that, it can affect the purchase decision of consumers on buying Korean products. This form of communication has valuable source credibility,

i.e. opinion leaders, co-workers, neighbors, friends, and relatives that are more likely to influence consumers' choice than any other source of information at little or no cost. Bradtke (2019) also specified that influence from friends and relatives or "word of mouth" is about 2.33 times more important as a factor influencing the consumer's decision. Further, Tor (2019) said that family and friends are the most credible sources of information for women who are considering a purchasing decision. Bradtke (2019) stated that millennials are heavy buyers of skincare products and word of mouth promotion have influence to their purchases (Salesforce Research Report, 2016).

According to Nielsen (2015), 92 percent of people trust recommendations from friends and family over any other type of advertising. Even academic research about word-of-mouth has proven its effectiveness in conversion (Kim, 2020). Many consumers check other consumer's recommendations before making any purchasing decision, especially when it comes to buying new products. Liu (2018) indicated that word-of-mouth is a key factor in making decisions on purchasing products and food. Burhanuddin (2016) supported and stated that word-of-mouth is accountable for 20 to 50 percent of all buying decisions.

In keeping with the discussion of several authors, approximately 90 percent of word-of-mouth still takes place offline. Word of mouth is accepted as the most powerful way to make decisions easier and quickens decision processes because it cuts through all the advertising clutter and simplifies marketing decisions. Sanchez (2019), stated that, positive recommendations from family and friends influenced about 62 percent of the Filipino respondents to try Korean beauty skincare products. The Nielsen Global Online Consumer Survey conducted in April of 2009 found that 90 percent of consumers trust recommendations from people they personally know, 70 percent trust online posts and brand websites, 62 percent trust television advertisements, and 59 percent trust magazine articles (Wee, 2016).

Methodology

Participants

The participants of the study were the millennials in Carmona, Cavite who have an experience in using Korean skin care products and have watched the list of Korean drama series prepared by the researchers. Moreover, the participants were 23 to 38 years old at the time of study, regardless of their sex, status, educational attainment, and monthly income. For this particular study, a total of 210 millennials were considered as participants of the study who met all the set characteristics above. The distribution sample of millennials in Carmona, Cavite is presented in Table 1 which was equally distributed in the different barangays in Carmona, Cavite.

Table 1. *Distribution of the participants in Carmona, Cavite*

<i>Barangay</i>	<i>Sample (N=210)</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Bancal	15	7.14
Cabilang Baybay	15	7.14
Lantic	15	7.14
Mabuhay	15	7.14
Maduya	15	7.14
Milagrosa	15	7.14
Poblacion 1	15	7.14
Poblacion 2	15	7.14
Poblacion 3	15	7.14
Poblacion 4	15	7.14
Poblacion 5	15	7.15
Poblacion 6	15	7.15
Poblacion 7	15	7.15
Poblacion 8	15	7.15
Total	210	100.00

Instrument

The adapted and modified questionnaires were used by the researchers in order to collect relevant information needed in the study. The first part of the instrument focused on the most used Korean skincare products of the participants. The second part identified the level of influence of product placement in Korean drama in terms of prominence, modality, and celebrity endorsement. The third part assessed the level of influence of word-of-mouth promotion in terms of traditional and electronic word of mouth. Meanwhile, the last part determined the level of participants' patronage decision towards Korean skincare products. A four-point Likert scale was used to measure the participants' responses accordingly: four (4) indicates strongly agree, three (3) for agree, two (2) for slightly agree, and one (1) for disagree.

Furthermore, pilot testing was done to test the reliability and to ensure the relevance of survey questionnaire in providing answers to the objectives of the present study. The survey questionnaire was distributed to thirty (30) Korean drama viewers and Korean skincare products users residing in General Mariano Alvarez, Cavite. The result of reliability test using Cronbach's Alpha on SPSS is accepted with 0.988 result.

Procedure

For the purpose of this study, a modified survey questionnaire was used in which a consent form was included on the first part in order to secure the participant's voluntary participation and to inform them on the benefits as well as the risks they might encounter in participating the study. The study also used gatekeeper questions in order to know if they belong to millennial generation, are users of Korean skincare products, and already watched Korean drama series provided by the researchers.

Due to the occurrence of pandemic, the gathering of data was done through online to secure the safety of both researchers and participants. The researchers utilized the Google form platform to easily distribute the survey questionnaires. The researchers coordinated with their family and friends who are living in Carmona, Cavite in disseminating the instrument. The link of Google form for the actual research survey was sent to each social media account of the participants particularly Facebook and Messenger.

For almost two months, the researchers posted their link every day to different Facebook pages and groups in the Municipality of Carmona and to the customized pages of the different barangays. The researchers also attempted many times to enter a group solely for Korean drama viewers, but the admin always rejected the request. They also strategized to caught the attention of the netizens by posting announcements regarding raffle event and prizes. They personally messaged unknown people from the list of their Facebook friends and some random people on different Facebook pages to identify participants who are qualified to be the part of the study (Appendix 16). After the gathering of data, the researchers started the tallying and analyzation of the collected data.

Ethical Considerations

Observing ethical standards in research is essential. At the core, this helped shape the true aims of the study, such as knowledge, truth,

and avoidance of error and promoted values essential to collaborative work, such as trust, accountability, mutual respect, and fairness. To ensure ethical research, this study followed and respected the principles of research ethics from the Belmont Report (2010). These principles respect a person's autonomy, beneficence and non-maleficence, justice, informed consent, confidentiality and data protection, integrity, and conflict of interest.

Results and Discussion

This section reveals the results of the study which are discussed with relevant references to answer the objectives of the study. This includes the discussion on the most used Korean skincare product brands; the level of influence of product placement in Korean drama in terms of prominence, modality, and celebrity endorsement; the level of influence of word-of-mouth promotion in terms of traditional and electronic word of mouth; the level of patronage decision of the participants; and the relationship between the said variables.

Most Used Korean Skincare Product Brands of Millennials in Carmona, Cavite

Table 2 presents the most used Korean skincare product brand of millennials in Carmona, Cavite. The results revealed that the most used brand was Innisfree with the highest percentage of 35 percent, followed by Mediheal with 26 percent. On the other hand, Manyo Factory and Klavvu with 3 percent were the least used Korean skincare product brands of the participants. This could be proven by the claims from the study of Capistrano (2018) saying that Innisfree is one of the most accessible Korean skincare brands to the customers due to its 11 stores present in the country. In addition, Innisfree is a brand known for being an eco-friendly product which has a good image in social media sites due to customer's excellent reviews and recommendations (Ariella & Yunus, 2019).

Table 2. *The most used Korean skincare product brands of the participants*

<i>Korean Skincare Product Brands</i>	<i>Frequency (N = 210)</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Laneige	43	21
Innisfree	75	35
Mediheal	54	26
Manyo Factory	6	3
CNP Laboratory	10	5
Klavvu	7	3
Colorgram	15	7
Total	210	100

Level of Influence of Product Placement in Korean drama

The level of influence of product placement in Korean drama on millennials in Carmona, Cavite towards Korean skincare products in terms of prominence, modality, and celebrity endorsement is presented in Table 3.

Table 3. *Level of influence of product placement in Korean drama on millennials in Carmona, Cavite towards Korean skincare products*

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Prominence	3.28	0.66	Highly Influential
Modality	3.21	0.65	Influential
Celebrity Endorsement	3.40	0.64	Highly Influential

Prominence. The result showed that the level of influence of product placement in terms of prominence in Korean drama on millennials in Carmona, Cavite towards Korean skincare products got a grand mean value of 3.28 which is interpreted as highly influential. This only shows that the subtle type of prominence definitely increases positive impression in the mind of the participants due to the plot-integration of skincare products on the storyline of Korean drama. Furthermore, the participants like it more if Korean skincare products are more noticeable and placed in a good position in Korean drama. Likewise, the participants see the scenes more realistic by using real Korean skincare products. Therefore, using a subtle type of prominence is effective; viewers will not be interrupted and feel uncomfortable while watching because product placement is done in an implicit way and eventually enables them to be curious and have the desire to try it.

The result is supported by the study of Hansson and Mattsson (2017) saying that placed products that are well integrated to the plot or are well blended to the storyline is an effective way of capturing the interest of the viewers while watching. The products should have something to do and should be relevant with the story to make the placement effective as it will not bother the viewers while watching.

Modality. The findings showed that the level of influence of product placement in Korean drama in terms of modality on millennials in Carmona, Cavite towards Korean skincare products got a grand mean value of 3.21 which is interpreted as influential. This means that the participants' decisions were averagely influenced by audio and visual presentation of skincare products to the scenes and dialogues in Korean drama. The participants have no problem with the placement of Korean skincare products that are both seen and mentioned at the same time. Furthermore, they do not mind when Korean skincare products are being mentioned and seen often in Korean drama. This implicates that combination of audio and visual modality is one of the positive approaches in using product placement because products are exposed to the viewers' minds once the products are mentioned and seen in the drama.

The result is aligned to the study of Adam and Hussain (2017) which claimed that the mixture of the two makes the product placement to affect the conscious and subconscious memory towards the product. Homer (2009) argued that the combination of audio and visual modality was more effective in affecting the minds of the viewers than using it individually.

Celebrity endorsement. The data revealed that the level of influence of product placement in terms of celebrity endorsement in Korean drama on millennials in Carmona, Cavite towards Korean skincare products got a grand mean value of 3.40 which is interpreted as highly influential. This means that the participants are definitely enticed to buy products since the Korean celebrities present on the drama are popular and really use the products promoted on the scene. Moreover, the findings implicate that the participants think that the positive publicity of celebrity endorsement is an important factor in influencing their decisions in purchasing Korean skincare products. In addition, they get attracted to buy Korean skincare products endorsed by a celebrity in Korean drama. This implies that in product placement, celebrity endorsement is important as it has a great influence because viewers tend to purchase what celebrities are using in the drama. The more the viewers idolize the celebrity present in the drama, the more they become interested to use the product.

The findings are in accordance to the study of Park (2015) which stated that Hallyu celebrity as an endorser is an effective way of marketing as most of their fans tend to adore and imitate the looks of their idols. Additionally, the study of Burhanuddin (2016) mentioned that celebrity endorsement showed that there is an impact on women's purchase decision whether to buy Korean cosmetic brand or Indonesian cosmetic brand. Some factors that influence for celebrity endorsement are visibility, credibility, attractiveness, and the power of the celebrity.

Level of Influence of Word-of-Mouth Promotion

The level of influence of word-of-mouth promotion on millennials in Carmona, Cavite towards Korean skincare products in terms of traditional word-of-mouth and electronic word of mouth is presented in Table 4.

Table 4. *Level of influence of word of mouth promotion on millennials in Carmona, Cavite towards Korean skincare products*

Indicator	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
Traditional Word of Mouth	3.33	0.66	Highly Influential
Electronic Word of Mouth	3.35	0.66	Highly Influential

Traditional word of mouth. The result showed that the level of influence of word-of-mouth promotion in terms of traditional word of mouth towards Korean Skincare products got a weighted mean value of 3.33 which is interpreted as highly influential. This means that the recommendations of family and friends in a face-to-face conversation highly stimulated the participants' decision to patronize Korean skincare products. Furthermore, the results revealed that the participants feel more comfortable buying something when they have gotten others opinion regarding skincare products. Likewise, participants believe the information they hear from people close to them than believing the ads. This indicates that in patronizing a product, the insights of other people who personally known by the customer becomes an important factor.

This is supported by the study of Sanchez (2019) wherein in the statistic showed in the recent survey conducted by Rakuten Insight, positive recommendations from family and friends influenced about 62 percent of the Filipino respondents who used Korean beauty skincare products.

Electronic word of mouth promotion. The data showed that the level of influence of word-of-mouth promotion in terms of electronic word of mouth towards Korean skincare products got a weighted mean value of 3.35 which is interpreted as highly influential. This means that reviews and comments on internet about Korean skincare products extremely urged participants to patronize it. Moreover, the results showed that the participants do read comments about the skincare products they will purchase. In addition, the participants always search for other's opinion about skincare products on the internet. Therefore, the customers tend to furtherly look the information about the product through the opinion of random people posted online before patronizing it.

This is aligned to the study of Moslehpour (2017) which discussed that consumers became interested in Korean cosmetics because they used the internet like official websites, dramas on YouTube, and reviews from many people to gather information about Korean cosmetic products. Moreover, according to Liu et al. (2019), 80 percent of the cosmetic consumers are affected by the information and comments made by other people on internet. Rosario (2020) also argued the same with the result of the previous and current study.

Level of Patronage Decision

Table 5 shows the level of patronage decision of millennials in Carmona, Cavite towards Korean skincare products.

Table 5. *Level of patronage decision of millennials in Carmona, Cavite towards Korean skincare products*

Indicator	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
Patronage Decision	3.26	0.69	Very High

The findings indicated that the level of patronage decision of millennials in Carmona, Cavite towards Korean skincare products got a weighted mean value of 3.26 which is interpreted as very high. This shows that the participants are affected by the promotional activities which extremely boost their decision to repurchase the Korean skincare products and will allow them to definitely share their positive experiences and recommend it to their friends and relatives. Furthermore, the participants are willing to have a repeat purchase of Korean skincare products if needed. Likewise, participants agreed to recommend Korean skincare products to their friends in the future. This means that product placement and word of mouth promotion are effective factors to make the customer purchase again the product and spread their own opinions about it.

The findings are supported by the study of Herman et al. (2016) in which they said that the popularity of Korean dramas has increased recognition and gained interest of the public towards Korean skincare products. Biagtan (2020) stated that Filipino women purchase Korean skincare products that are shown in Korean dramas. In addition, Erkan and Evan (2016) stated that social networking sites give an opportunity for the customers to spread their opinions and reviews in order to help other customers in purchasing a product.

Relationship Between the Level of Influence of Product Placement in Korean Drama and the Level of Patronage Decision of the Participants

The relationship between the level of influence of product placement in Korean drama in terms of prominence, modality, and celebrity endorsement; and the level of patronage decision of millennials towards Korean skincare products in Carmona, Cavite is shown in Table 6. The result revealed that all factors of product placement in Korean drama have a significant relationship to patronage decision. Therefore, product placement as promotional strategy is indeed effective in persuading the participants to patronize Korean skin care products.

Table 6. Relationship between product placement in Korean Drama and patronage decision

<i>Variables</i>	<i>P-Value</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Prominence and Patronage Decision	0.001	Significant
Modality and Patronage Decision	0.002	Significant
Celebrity Endorsement and Patronage Decision	0.001	Significant

a = significance level of 0.05

Prominence and patronage decision. The result shows that there is a significant relationship between prominence and patronage decision of millennials living in Carmona, Cavite towards Korean skincare products. This means that prominence played an important role in affecting the patronage decision of the participants towards Korean skincare products due to the plot-integration of the products on the storyline of Korean drama which further leads to a positive impression in their minds.

The result has the same stand with the study of Hansson and Mattsson (2017), and Gurses and Okan (2014) which stated that product placement will be really effective if the product is well blended to the storyline or have something to do or relevant with the story which leads in changing the viewers purchasing behaviors, unconsciously.

Modality and patronage decision. The findings reveal that modality has a significant relationship with the patronage decision of millennials in Carmona, Cavite towards Korean skincare products. The result manifests that the participants think modality has a positive influence to their patronage decision towards Korean skincare products by being involved in Korean drama through the scenes and dialogues (audio and visual presentation).

The result of this study argues the same with the findings of Du (2013), and Utomo and Suprajitno (2020) who revealed that high modality (audio-visual mode) helps the product placement to be effective by shaping the viewers mind to unconsciously think the information in purchasing the product which further enables them to actually buy the product.

Celebrity endorsement and patronage decision. The study indicates that celebrity endorsement has a significant relationship with the patronage decision of millennials residing in Carmona, Cavite towards Korean skincare products. This only signifies that celebrity endorsement is an effective factor because the participants were enticed by the popular Korean celebrity present on the drama who uses skincare products promoted on the scene, which enables them to buy the product.

The result of the study coincides with the findings of Nelson et al. (2017) which claimed that celebrity endorsement positively affects the audience attention and their patronage decision. Furthermore, Burhanuddin (2016) stated that the Korean stars who made the Korean products popular allow the viewers to imitate them, which signifies that they are capable of influencing the purchase decisions of the viewers.

Relationship Between the Level of Influence of Word-of-Mouth Promotion and the Level of Patronage Decision of the Participants

The relationship between the level of influence of word-of-mouth promotion in terms of traditional and electronic word of mouth and the level of patronage decision of millennials towards Korean skincare products in Carmona, Cavite is shown in Table 7. The result revealed that both traditional and electronic word of mouth promotion have a significant relationship to patronage decision. This means that word of mouth promotion is an effective promotional strategy to influence the patronage decision of the participants.

Table 7. Relationship between word-of-mouth promotion and patronage decision

Variables	P-Value	Interpretation
Traditional Word of Mouth and Patronage Decision	0.029	Significant
Electronic Word of Mouth and Patronage Decision	0.001	Significant

a = significance level of 0.05

Traditional word of mouth and patronage decision. The result shows that there is a significant relationship between the level of influence of traditional word of mouth and the level of patronage decision of millennials living in Carmona, Cavite towards Korean skincare products. This means that traditional word of mouth impacted the patronage decision of the participants towards Korean skincare products through the recommendations of their friends and family in a face-to-face manner.

According to Bradtke (2019), millennials are the heavy buyers of Korean skincare products and traditional word of mouth promotion has an influence to their purchases. Furthermore, Sanchez (2019) claimed that about 62 percent of the Filipinos were persuaded by their family and friend's positive recommendations which makes them to keep on buying Korean skincare products.

Electronic word of mouth promotion and patronage decision. The findings of the study show that the level of influence of electronic word of mouth promotion has a significant relationship with the level of patronage decision of the participants towards Korean skincare products. This means that the participants' patronage decisions towards Korean skincare products were urged through reading posts, reviews, and comments on the internet.

The outcome is aligned to the study of Gómez-Suárez et al. (2017) which discussed that as a result of technological advances, the new means of communication have led to changes not just in consumer behavior but also on purchase decision as the influence enables the consumers to exert on each by allowing them to obtain or share information about companies, products, or brands (Gómez-Suárez et al., 2017).

Conclusions

The most used Korean skincare product brands of millennials in Carmona, Cavite among the seven choices were Innisfree and Mediheal. Therefore, it is concluded that in this study, these two Korean skin care product brands were the most used and most patronized brands by the millennials.

For the level of influence of product placement in Korean drama in terms of prominence and celebrity endorsement, the result showed a very high influence. This implies that the millennials considered the plot- integration of skincare products on the storyline and the Korean celebrities present on Korean drama as a highly influential factor in patronizing Korean skincare products. In terms of modality, the millennials considered it as influential which indicates that they somehow pay attention to the audio and visual presentation of skincare products shown in Korean drama.

For the level of influence of word-of-mouth promotion, traditional and electronic word of mouth promotion are both highly influential. Whether it is traditional or electronic word of mouth promotion, participants are considering others' recommendation and reviews. Word of mouth is indeed a great marketing strategy for Korean products. Millennials give importance to the recommendation and opinions of people surrounding them whether it is physical or virtual.

There is also a very high level of patronage decision of millennials towards Korean skin care products in Carmona, Cavite. It showed that the millennial's patronage decision was influenced by the product placement in Korean drama and word of mouth promotion. This also means that the exposure of Korean skincare products in Korean drama and the recommendations of other people whether in a face-to-face manner or over the internet lead the millennials to patronize Korean skincare products.

For the relationship of the level of influence of product placement in Korean drama in terms of prominence, modality, and celebrity endorsement, the result revealed a significant relationship to the level of patronage decision of the participants. This explains that Korean drama really has an effect to the viewers. This only signifies that all factors of product placement in Korean drama make the millennials from Carmona, Cavite to patronize the Korean skincare products they have seen in the said dramas.

Lastly, the level of influence of word-of-mouth promotion in terms of traditional and electronic have a significant relationship to the level of patronage decision. This implicates that both recommendations in a face- to-face conversation brought by families and friends, as well as by searching and reading comments, posts, and reviews of random people over the internet shape their decisions to patronize the Korean skincare products.

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